

Food Plants Used by Tribals of Mount Parasnath and Adjacent Areas in Giridih District, Jharkhand, India

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Abstract: An ethnobotanical study was carried out among the tribals of Mount Parasnath and adjacent areas in Giridih district, Jharkhand to document food plants of tribal utility. The 40 plant species belonging to 36 genera and 30 families were collected which are being used by tribals as supplementary source of food.

Key Words: Mount Parasnath, Tribal, Ethnobotany, Food plants.

1. INTRODUCTION

Mount Parasnath and its adjacent area lies in the mid-eastern part of Chotanagpur highland which located between 86° 03' E to 86° 14' E longitudes and 23° 55' N to 24° 01' N latitudes, it forms the southern parts of Giridih district. The available literature indicates that different tribes utilize various plant and plant parts (Anderson, 1863; Alagesaboopathi et.al., 1996; Gaur et.al., 1983; Janardhanan et.al., 2003; Negi et.al., 1991; Oommachan et.al., 1988). We added some more plants available in our localities. Legumes include many very important crop plants that contribute very critical protein to the diet of both humans and animals around the world. The area is inhabited by large number of tribes like Kol, Birhore, Birijia, Kairo, Kheria etc. They live in close vicinity of the forests and depend on forest products for their day to day needs. The edible parts of the wild plants are the best source of vitamins, minerals and nutritional elements for the forest dwellers. The forests are mainly of monsoon sub-humid or tropical moist deciduous type. Vegetation growing in these forests plays a vital role in the economy and health of tribals.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

Ethnobotanical surveys were conducted in various parts of Giridih district (Bhirhi, Bringadha, Darang, Jainagar, Jarabad, Khargi, Korhatarh, Madhuban, Mojpur, Shrijubbhi, Sugatarh etc.). Information on traditionally used food plants were collected by discussion with the village chieftains and informants etc. As a result of the discussion plant parts used, their mode of uses was recorded. The specimens were collected by Yadava and properly identified in the Botany Research Lab, Udai Pratap Autonomous College, Varanasi.

In the present paper only the wild plants used by the tribes as food (raw or cooked or processed), have been discussed.

3. ENUMERATION:

Alangium salvifolium L.f. (Alangiaceae, Akarkanta) *RVY 13105

Ripe or unripe fruits are used as pickles.

Antidesma bunius Spreng. (Euphorbiaceae, Amati, Naikuti) RVY 13147

Ripe fruits are edible.

Bauhinia vahlii Roxb. (Caesalpinaceae, Taur, Rung) RVY 13015

Seeds are cooked and eaten.

Berberis asiatica Roxb. (Berberidaceae, Rasaut) RVY 13047

Dried berries are edible.

Bombax ceiba L. (Bombacaceae, Semul or Simal) RVY 13092

Young roots and flower buds are eaten in green salad, gum are also edible.

Butea monosperma (Lamk.) Taub. (Papilionaceae, Palas or Dhak) RVY 13010

Gums are edible.

- Capparis zeylanica* L. (Capparidaceae, Ardanda) RVY 13059
Raw fruits are edible.
- Careya arborea* Roxb. (Lecythidaceae, Kumbhi) RVY 13033
Ripe or unripe fruits are edible.
- Cissus adnata* Roxb. (Vitaceae, Nadena) RVY 13051
Leaves are cooked and eaten as vegetable.
- Cissus repanda* Vahl (Vitaceae, Pureni) RVY 13106
Young shoots are cooked and taken as vegetable.
- Cleome monophylla* L. (Capparidaceae, Hurhura) RVY 13055
Raw seeds are edible as vegetable rich in iron 24.45 mg/ 100 gm seeds.
- Cordia dichotoma* Forst. (Boraginaceae, Bhairala) RVY 13148
Fruits are edible after cooking, pickled and eaten.
- Dillenia indica* L. (Dilleniaceae, Chalita or Chalta) RVY 13008
Calyx of fruits is cooked and eaten as vegetable; boiled flower is edible.
- Ehretia laevis* Roxb. (Boraginaceae, Chamror, Koda, Tambolia) RVY 13042
Bark and raw fruits are taken as vegetable.
- Flacourtia romantchi* L' Herit. (Flacourtiaceae, Bilangra) RVY 13132
Ripe fruits are edible.
- Fragaria vesca* L. (Rosaceae, Pahari rasbhari) RVY 13037
Ripe and unripe fruits are aromatic, tasty, eaten rich in protein and vit. C.
- Grewia elastica* Royle (Tiliaceae, Phalsa) RVY 13122
Ripe fruits are edible to nutritive purposes.
- Lagerstroemia parviflora* Roxb. (Lythraceae, Jarul) RVY 13123
Gums are sweet and edible.
- Madhuca indica* J.F. Gmel. (Sapotaceae, Mahua) RVY 13014
Flowers and raw fruits are edible to nutritive value.
- Miliusa tomentosa* (Roxb.) J. Sinclair. (Anonaceae, Kari, Kirua) RVY 13124
Ripe fruits are eaten.
- Moringa oleifera* Lamk. (Moringaceae, Saunjana) RVY 13002
Flowers, fruits and leaves are cooked and eaten as vegetable.
- Mucuna cochinchinesis* Cheval. (Papilionaceae, Khamach, Kawanch) RVY 13096
Its pods and seeds are edible, fruits and seeds eaten after removal of velvet skin.
- Murraya koenigii* Spreng. (Rutaceae, Karipatta) RVY 13088
Leaves used for flavouring curries, raw fruits are edible.
- Physalis minima* L. (Solanaceae, Tulatipatti) RVY 13027
Fruits and leaves are cooked and edible as vegetable.
- Polyalthia cerasoides* Benth. (Anonaceae, Kudumi, Sandi) RVY13178
Ripe fruits are eaten.
- Polygala tatarinowii* Regel. (Polygalaceae, Meradu) RVY 13085
Tender leaves are eaten as vegetable.
- Pueraria tuberosa* DC. (Papilionaceae, Vidari kand) RVY 13170
Green tender foliage nutritive and is eaten, tubers sometimes weight up to 40 gm each eaten after cooking.
- Santalum album* L. (Santalaceae, Chandan) RVY 13114
Roasted seeds are edible.
- Schleichera oleosa* (Lour.) Oxen. (Sapindaceae, Kusum) RVY 13045
Seeds oil, raw fruits and shoots are eaten as vegetable.
- Semecarpus anacardium* L. f. (Anacardiaceae, Bhelwa) RVY 13053
The fleshy fruit is eaten.
- Shorea robusta* Gaertn. f. (Dipterocarpaceae, Sal or Sakhu) RVY 13054
Seeds oil edible as vegetable.
- Sonchus oleraceus* L. (Asteraceae, Dudhi) RVY 13019
Plant edible as vegetable.
- Sonchus wightianus* DC. (Asteraceae, Sahadevi) RVY 13011
Young shoots eaten as salad, leaves as vegetables.
- Sterculia foetida* L. (Sterculiaceae, Pinari) RVY 13153

Roasted seeds are eaten, large quantity causes abortion in ladies.

Sterculia urens Roxb. (Sterculiaceae, Gular or Kulu) RVY 13136

Tree gum *Karaya* are edible, roasted seeds and seed oil are edible.

Sterculia villosa Roxb. (Sterculiaceae, Udal or Gulkandar) RVY 13173

Seeds are eaten after roasting.

Syzygium wallichii (W.) Walp. (Myrtaceae, Jamun) RVY 13112

Ripe fruits are eaten.

Terminalia chebula Retz obs. (Combretaceae, Harra) RVY 13029

Gum are edible.

Tetrastigma lanceolarium (Roxb.) Plachon (Vitaceae, Bherseri) RVY 13097

Fruits are eaten raw or cooked.

Zizyphus oenoplia Mill. (Rhamnaceae, Mahkua or Makoh) RVY 13080

Ripe or unripe fruits are edible.

*Field diary number

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

In the enumeration, plant species are arranged alphabetically with their correct names, local names, name of family, field diary number and part used with mode of traditional preparation. The data have been presented.

The current status and future prospects of challenges of the following: in vitro morphogenesis; biotic and abiotic stress tolerance; genomic; nitrogen fixation and utilization; nutritional improvement and biodiversity of wild and tribal legumes. These plants can be of great help in times of scarcity and famine due to drought and flood. In fact, they play a vital role in the tribal economy and the culture.

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